

SoK: A Comprehensive Threat Model of Intelligent Mobile Interfaces: An Examination of Remote National ID Registration Case

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Abstract—Developing an intelligent user interface brings together design, artificial intelligence (AI), and software development teams. With recent advances in AI development, we have witnessed the transformation of many traditional software applications into intelligent ones. However, existing threat modelling strategies fail to adequately address the unique requirements of an intelligent user interface (IUI). An IUI relies on machine learning models that can produce different outputs based on the provided data. This dynamic behaviour results in alternative user journey paths. Consequently, the model’s behaviour is highly dependent on the training data and algorithms. Therefore, security analysis should consistently consider both development-time and production-time threats proactively. In this paper, we elucidate our strategy for threat modelling a prototype of a remote national ID registration mobile application that incorporates intelligent modules for biometric data collection. Drawing on knowledge from the fields of cybersecurity and responsible AI, we outline the essential steps for threat modelling mobile intelligent applications based on our experiences with this use case.

1. Introduction

The definition of *intelligent user interfaces* (IUI) may vary in different contexts. IUI researchers employ the term *intelligence* with key aspects of automation, adaptation, and interaction, often associated with various descriptors like ‘user interface,’ ‘system,’ or ‘agent’ [40]. A broad definition includes any interface that incorporates a computational intelligence component [12], [19]. In our use case, the intelligent user interface is a system that utilizes computer vision models to easily obtain biometrics through the mobile device camera. Therefore, our system is not an agent that continuously learns from data, but rather a mobile application that demonstrates intelligence through previously acquired features.

Threat modelling is a structured and systematic approach to identifying and mitigating security threats and vulnerabilities in software applications or hardware systems [29]. In our context, we are more interested in the software application part, where threat modelling is a crucial component of the application security lifecycle. Threat modelling helps to understand the potential risks and weaknesses in an application, allowing security professionals to proactively address security issues before they can be exploited by attackers. In the application development lifecycle, threat modelling can be conducted in different stages or continuously throughout the process.

A continuous threat modelling approach starts in the early stages of product development to prevent costly security breaches and data compromises [4]. Following this approach, we conducted preliminary threat modelling to identify potential threats and mitigate them in the initial phases of the development process before the programming stage. We started our analysis by decomposing the application into subprocesses, then we identified the adversaries and threat actors, assessed the threats and finally extended our assessment for AI-related threats and human-system interaction.

The first part of threat assessment including STRIDE and MITRE ATT&CK follows a parallel flow of approaches to MITRE’s TARA (Threat Assessment and Remediation Analysis) methodology [44]. It involves identifying potential threats, assessing vulnerabilities, evaluating risks, analyzing countermeasures, and developing remediation plans. The methodology encourages ongoing monitoring and continuous improvement to adapt to evolving cyber risks, making it a structured and systematic approach for enhancing an organization’s cybersecurity posture.

STRIDE is a threat modelling framework used in cybersecurity to identify and categorise potential threats or vulnerabilities in a system or application [17], [33]. The acronym STRIDE stands for:

- Spoofing (S): This involves attackers pretending to be someone or something else to gain unauthorized access.
- Tampering (T): Tampering threats refer to unauthorized changes or alterations to data or code.
- Repudiation (R): Repudiation threats involve the denial of actions or events by users or systems.
- Information Disclosure (I): This threat category encompasses unauthorized access to or exposure to sensitive information.
- Denial of Service (DoS): In a DoS attack, the goal is to disrupt the availability of a system or service.
- Elevation of Privilege (EoP): This threat involves attackers gaining unauthorized access to higher levels of privilege or authority within a system or application.

STRIDE can be applied to entities or interactions: (1) *STRIDE-per-element* applies STRIDE threats for each component, including identifying how they could be spoofed, tampered with, used for repudiation, or leaked information. (2) *STRIDE-per-interaction* analyzes the specific interactions that occur between different parts of the system, such as data flows or communication channels.

Figure 1. Our threat modelling approach to analyze the threats of mobile national ID registration use case includes three main steps: (1) Case analysis to decompose the scenario and define the interactions, (2) Threat assessment with STRIDE and MITRE ATT&CK frameworks, (3) Extended assessment to analyze AI-related threats and human behaviours further.

STRIDE stands as a solid starting point for initiating threat modelling due to its well-established reputation and widespread adoption within the cybersecurity community. As a recognized, highly utilized, documented and mature threat modelling framework, the findings of a STRIDE analysis are understandable and reproducible by the majority of security practitioners, making it an ideal choice for articulating and comprehending threats effectively [14]. Furthermore, its ubiquity is reflected in the extensive support provided by many existing threat modelling diagramming tools (e.g. OWASP Threat Dragon, Microsoft TMT) for the STRIDE framework by default. This built-in compatibility streamlines the modelling process, ensuring that security assessments are conducted with ease and efficiency, consequently enhancing the overall security posture of the system under evaluation [34].

Nevertheless, it is imperative to acknowledge that STRIDE has certain limitations, particularly in the realm of identifying intricate adversarial behaviours, a concern that arises primarily in the context of multi-stage cyber-attacks where physical components are deployed as attack agents. To effectively address the challenges posed by these sophisticated attack vectors, a more comprehensive threat modelling framework may be warranted to ensure that the evolving threat landscape is appropriately addressed [32].

MITRE ATT&CK (Adversarial Tactics, Techniques, and Common Knowledge) is a comprehensive framework for understanding and categorizing the tactics, techniques, and procedures (TTPs) that adversaries use to compromise and exploit systems and networks [36]. The framework is divided into two main categories: Enterprise and Mobile. While Using MITRE ATT&CK in threat modelling, we

first identify relevant techniques that could be leveraged by potential attackers to compromise the system. This helps in understanding the potential attack vectors. Once the tactics and techniques are identified for potential threats, we develop mitigation strategies and security controls to defend against these threats. MITRE ATT&CK provides information on common mitigations and defensive techniques for each technique.

While the STRIDE and MITRE ATT&CK frameworks can provide a comprehensive analysis for software and remote-server level attacks, an IUI also relies on AI-powered components. These frameworks do not cover the possible attacks in the AI development flow. Recently, MITRE introduced its ATLAS framework, which follows the same TTP approach to AI development security [24]. While it is not as established as the Enterprise and Mobile frameworks, it provides a good starting point for identifying and investigating possible threats. Due to the rapid pace of development in AI models, specialised research is required to identify possible mitigations for each technique after the tactics and techniques have been identified.

A threat model that includes STRIDE, MITRE ATT&CK, and MITRE ATLAS, encompasses most of the possible security concerns in an IUI development. However, these frameworks are still limited in their ability to understand human behaviour and human-system interaction. A mobile IUI, by its nature, exhibits ubiquitous features, serving as a natural interface seamlessly integrated into its environment. It does not only engage with its end-users but also with its surroundings. Therefore, it is imperative to investigate interactions between the system and end-users, as well as interactions with the environment, to identify potential physical space attacks.

Human-AI interaction and responsible AI development guidelines can be used as security suggestions to help us understand possible adversarial behaviours and mitigate them with our design choices. In our analysis, we utilized the *Decision Tree for the Responsible Application of Artificial Intelligence*, which is a guide designed by AAAS to help individuals and organizations put into practice a set of ethical principles related to AI [1]. Further, we also brought the integrated behaviour model to better understand the motives of end-users, their surroundings and potential attackers. Although it is mainly used in psychological and health-related studies, it presents a structured model to understand the behaviours in certain conditions. It emphasizes the importance of attitudes, beliefs, subjective norms, and self-efficacy in shaping human behaviour [25]. The responsibility guidelines with behavioural models complete our extended analysis to better understand the possible attack points and scenarios.

Figure 1 depicts the main steps of the overall threat modelling approach for developing a mobile IUI. In our mobile IUI development, remote national ID registration application, collecting sensitive data brings different levels of security concerns during the registration, verification, and authentication processes. However, this paper exclusively addresses high-level considerations that have guided us in presenting a threat modelling approach tailored for a range of mobile user interface implementations. We followed a top-bottom approach in this threat model, where we first reported an analysis for high-level flow. Then, we detailed each operation. An advantage of this structured hierarchical approach is its generalizability; it is not bound to any specific implementation or product deployment. This implementation-agnostic approach can also support the integration of continuous threat modelling by listing by producing a high-level, understandable report that can be understood and interpreted by multi-disciplinary teams.

This paper contributes to the cybersecurity domain in two ways: (1) By incorporating insights from the cybersecurity domain and other fields to create a comprehensive preliminary threat model for a mobile biometric application, and (2) By applying this combined knowledge to establish a foundation for a future threat model and attack taxonomy for mobile IUIs. The subsequent sections of this paper outline our threat modelling approach for the remote ID registration scenario and detail its expansion to develop a threat modelling mechanism for mobile IUIs.

2. Use Case: Mobile National ID Registration

In this use case, the mobile IUI is a remote ID registration application. Using this application, *citizen* provides demographic information, documents, biometrics, and address information to obtain access to government services. If the *citizen* cannot provide the necessary validation information through documents, a trusted *introducer* can vouch for the *citizen*. Based on the trust level of provided information, the *issuer* (e.g. Government Home Office) gives the citizen access to different levels of government services. Figure 2 illustrates a high-level process sequence through an ID registration process using the mobile application. In this flow, the main processes include collecting demographic information, scanning documents, collecting

Figure 2. The flow diagram of the proposed remote ID registration scenario. If the citizen has no access to any document that can support identification, they can continue the process with an Introducer. If they have documents

fingerprints and face biometrics and submitting this information to the issuer.

A national ID registration through a mobile application brings unique development requirements such as carefully considering the cultural implications, collecting sensitive information such as biometrics, and accessing data by multiple parties. (1) **Social/cultural interactions:** Understanding this context can help security researchers understand possible motivations for attackers. For example, an attacker can aim at a certain ethnic group if there is an ongoing debate for accelerating ID registration efforts in a conflicted zone. (2) **AI-powered biometrics:** Our application uses three different AI-powered modules. Current threat analysis methods show limited ability to cover all threats in the planning, training, and inference steps of an ML pipeline. (3) **Multi-party involvement:** The same application can be used by a citizen, a citizen with an introducer, and a citizen with a government official. This kind of context dependency requires changing trust levels at the software and hardware levels. Hence, personally identifiable information (PII) of the citizen will be physically visible to the introducer and government officials.

2.1. Biometric Data and Stakeholder’s Responsibilities

When designing an application that collects, processes and submits biometric data that directly links to their real-life identities, we should follow human rights in the application and data collection processes. Hert et al. propose five principles for achieving human-rights aligned

Threat Actor	Goals & Motivations	Capabilities	Access	Resources
End User (Non-hostile)	Accidental & No-malicious intent	Limited	Internal	Minimal
End User (Hostile)	Discontent	Limited	Internal	Minimal
Anarchist	Damage	Limited	External	Limited knowledge and financial
Civil Activists	Embarrassment	Adept	External	Moderate knowledge and financial
Corrupt Government Official	Business Advantage	Adept	Internal	Internal knowledge
Disgruntled Employee	Discontent	Operational	Internal	Internal knowledge
Nation-State Level Spy	Business/ Technical Advantage	Adept	External	Extensive knowledge, financial and equipment
Internal Spy	Acquisition/ Theft	Adept	Internal	Internal knowledge
Terrorist	Damage	Adept	External	Moderate knowledge and financial
Thief	Acquisition/ Theft	Limited	Internal	Internal knowledge
Vandal	Damage	Operational	External	Limited knowledge and financial
Vendor	Business Advantage	Operational	Internal	Organisation size related

TABLE 1. THREAT ACTOR PROFILES

privacy-by-design (PbD) solutions in the biometrics domain [9], that are also aligned with the existing biometrics security and privacy standards: (1) Raw biometric data should not be stored in a way that is easily accessible to unauthorized individuals. (2) Fingerprints, which are considered sensitive data, should not be collected without the individual’s consent. (3) Biometric data should not be shared with third parties without the individual’s consent. (4) Biometric data should be encrypted to protect it from unauthorized access. (5) If an individual is rejected based on their biometric data, the decision should be reviewed to ensure that it was not made in a discriminatory manner.

In this sense, we should keep all the biometric data safe throughout the process and while keeping them safe, we should ensure that citizens can obtain their ID to access vital governmental services. To better understand the assets in this domain, we also followed the ISO 29196:2018 standard, which explains the possible weaknesses in enrolment, verification and identification processes. Based on this standard, in a standard application process, the *Attendant* (citizen) is responsible for providing the best biometric samples possible. The *Enrolment Officer* and *Enrolment Authority* are responsible for collecting the biometrics and ensuring the quality. *Vendors* employ designers and developers to develop secure and responsible biometric services complying with the standards and guidelines developed by *Regulators*. Compared to standard registration processes, a mobile registration differs in the presence of an enrolment officer which brings additional concerns about the reliability of the enrolment process. Our threat model provides insight into possible security concerns for vendors.

2.2. Identifying Adversaries

Prior to studying the attack points, it is important to study about adversaries. The term threat actor denotes an individual or a group who can execute a threat. The threat actors can vary from state-sponsored actors to individual hackers, organized criminal networks, and terrorist groups. Another significant factor that has been generally neglected is the insider risks that are either deliberate or accidental and posed through improper usage or lack of

knowledge. Understanding the motivations and characteristics of the threat actors is a critical step of the risk assessment. We aimed to identify threat actors which are able to pose high risk, rather than identifying the vulnerabilities in the attack surfaces of the analysed system. To identify threat actors, we used two libraries which are also utilized in MITRE’s TARA methodology: Threat Agent Library (TAL), and the Methods and Objectives Library (MOL).

TAL library includes twenty-three unique threat actor profiles and multiple associated attributes of these. There are types of hostile and non-hostile agents e.g., mobsters, legal adversaries, terrorists, cyber vandals, corrupt government officials, government cyber-warrior, disgruntled employees or distracted, untrained or reckless employees [7]. Each threat actor is defined by his/her intent (hostile or accidental attack), access (internal or external), impact (i.e. acquisition/theft, business advantage, damage, embarrassment, or technical advantage), limits (i.e. code of conduct, legal, extra-legal-minor, and extra-legal-major), skill level (i.e. individual, club, contest, team, organisation, and government), objective (i.e. copy, destroy, inflict harm, retract data), and visibility (i.e. overt, covert and secretive).

The list of prevalent motivations is introduced in [6] with respect to threat actors. A threat actor may also have co-motivations and personal motivations besides the defining motivations. Personal motivations may be useful to distinguish the individual threat actors from the groups. However, we focus on the defining motivations of the threat actors in this study to simplify the threat analysis. The potential threat actors against mobile IUIs are derived from the TAL classifications and presented in Table 2.

This profile table presents a generic set of threat actors that is useful for identifying possible attacks and their motivations. However, it is also limited to identifying personal and context-dependent motivations. To extend our analysis, we employed the *integrated behaviour model* to better analyse attacker motivations and goals.

2.3. Understanding the Human Behaviour

Although TAL and MOL libraries provide a comprehensive list of threat actors, it is limited in terms

of covering all the motives of the attackers, specifically personal motivations from the *end user* perspective. In our scenario, a citizen can complete the registration process with the assistance of an introducer if they lack valid documents to prove their identity. This introducer could be a village head, a teacher, a doctor, or any trusted individual with a valid identity. While this approach simplifies the registration process in many instances, it also raises various security concerns. In our case, it's crucial to analyze the potential behaviours of stakeholders before proposing a nationwide solution.

We employed *integrated behaviour model* to structure this analysis. This model is easy to interpret and focuses on a person's attitudes, perceived norms, and personal agency [25]. Within this model, the most critical factor is motive, as without a motive, we cannot explain behaviour. Furthermore, behavioural intention is determined by attitude, perceived norms, and personal agency. Additionally, an individual must possess the knowledge and skills to carry out a particular behaviour. Therefore, by understanding the motive, identifying the necessary skills and knowledge, and considering environmental factors, we can define potential attacks based on the attacker's motive and establish mitigations based on the attacker's skills, environmental constraints, and habitual behaviours.

We analyzed behaviours and derived intentions based on the attacker's proximity to the citizen, technological expertise, and motive:

- **Citizen-self:** A citizen may exhibit malicious behaviour to establish a new identity, possibly due to criminal intentions or a desire to gain access to certain government services. Or, another motivation can be financial gain, where the citizen may attempt to defraud the system to gain access to government services, such as subsidies or welfare benefits. In such cases, the citizen would need to enrol with new biometrics. In disadvantaged areas, we anticipate lower expertise (e.g., limited ability to create 3D makeup disguises), but a higher potential for coercion (as there may be fewer official figures to act as deterrents against individuals resorting to bribery or threats, etc.).
- **Inner circle (Friend/Relative):** In this scenario, the attacker may be motivated to access government services under the victim citizen's name. The attacker might seek a personal vendetta. In this case, harming citizen's reputations or disrupting their life might be a goal.
- **Outer circle:** In this situation, the attacker may have some knowledge of the citizen's name and limited access to photos but cannot easily obtain the citizen's biometrics. In this case, the attack might aim to create multiple new identities with the names of the known citizens without valid identities. These new citizens might be used for economic interests or create new groups for any other kind of political or ideological interest.
- **Complete Stranger:** In this case, the attacker possesses no information about the citizen, but their actions can result in negative experiences for the citizen. The primary motive of the attacker may be to target the entire system. This could

lead to denial-of-service type attacks. Historically, we've observed such attacks carried out for amusement, anarchy, to demonstrate skills, or to disrupt government services. We presented the possible threat actors from the *complete stranger* class in Table 2 as elaborated in the previous section.

2.4. Identifying Attack Points (APs)

Throughout the main sequence of processes (Figure 2), document scanning and biometric collection (including fingerprint and facial data) make use of camera-based services. These processes access the camera, utilize the camera sensor to capture images, extract the features, and store this feature set. After collecting data on the mobile application, extracted features are employed within a template-matching algorithm for use in the decision module on the server side. Given that these processes all involve a common camera-based collection process (CCP), they also share a similar machine learning (ML) module development workflow. Within the ML development flow, developers utilize the collected data to train the models, evaluate their models using test datasets, and then deploy these models for inference. In this context, we should consider both production-time and development-time security concerns to present a complete analysis. We combined production-time and development-time threats in Figure 3 to show all possible threats that link to camera-based services.

The attack points for the camera-based collection process are based on a recent review on biometrics security [16]. These attack points can either be processes or communication channels. Similarly, in the ML module development (MLMD) part, we focused on six attack points. These development-time attack points are identified based on a recent review [15].

2.4.1. Production-time Attack Points. The only platform-specific analysis to identify attack points was identifying security principles and software-hardware communication channels in Android OS. The Android OS architecture is structured into layers that enable effective and secure communication between software and hardware. The Linux kernel serves as the foundation, managing core system functions, while the Hardware Abstraction Layer (HAL) acts as an intermediary, providing a standardized interface for software to interact with diverse hardware components [3]. Native libraries offer core functionality, and the Android Runtime (ART) executes application code. The Application Framework supplies higher-level services for apps to access device features, and user applications run at the top. The HAL's role in abstracting hardware details ensures software compatibility across various Android devices and provides a secure layer.

The API-based structure with HAL restricts direct access to hardware, which automatically mitigates several security concerns that could result in obtaining raw biometric information through security channels. Although the risk is low, we still identified them as possible attack points which are denoted as P002 and P004 in Figure 3. This figure illustrates the main processes in the mobile application, identifies possible attack points through

Figure 3. Possible attack points for the production and development flows.

these processes on-device and server-side, and lists the development-time threats for the AI-related tasks.

The acronyms for the attack points system are structured as follows: P00X, where P stands for *production-time* and X represents the numerical order of the attack point. We’ve maintained this numbering system consistently with the reference material from [16], which served as the foundation for our biometrics attack points. In Table 3, certain attack points are omitted (for instance, P012 is not present). These omissions are intentional and have been made to align our attack point numbering with the framework established by the aforementioned reference work. We describe these attack points in Table 3.

2.4.2. Development-time Attack Points. In a machine learning development flow, there are various attack points where security threats or vulnerabilities can be exploited. Similar to our approach in identifying attack points in the production-time flow, we identified development-time attack points based on a recent review [15].

Traditional ML development can be summarized in five main processes: (1) *Data Collection and Storage* can be challenged via data poisoning and data leakage attacks. (2) Then, this data is used in *processing and training a model*, where we can observe feature extraction vulnerabilities, model poisoning and evasion: Crafting inputs to mislead the model during training. (3) *Evaluating a model* can be seen as part of the training, but we identify it as a separate attack point to focus possible attacks

on test datasets. (4) *Model Deployment* is the step in which the production-ready model is moved online, where enterprise-level attacks might occur. (5) Throughout the *inference*, we should monitor and maintain the model and check for model decay, data drift and model updates. We describe these attack points and possible attacks detailly in Table 4.

2.5. STRIDE in Action

The first step of STRIDE analysis is defining trust boundaries to understand the potential issues in changing trust levels. Since we plan to collect all data and extract all features on-device, the main trust boundaries result from the data transitions between hardware, HAL and software levels. As we elaborated in the previous section, the relationship between the software, hardware, and hardware abstraction layer is based on Android documentation, and it is valid for above Android 10 (also known as Android Q) (Latest version: Android 14). We chose Android 10 to benefit from the abstracted secure media service while utilizing the camera.

In this threat model, we did not explicitly focus on server-side operations but analyzed biometric-related operations that can possibly occur remotely. Based on the stated principles and Android documentation on hardware abstraction architecture, the main trust boundaries for a sample data flow are drawn between the software layer,

application database, hardware abstraction layer (HAL), and hardware. The data flows of Table 2 are based on these trust boundaries. All the collected data through the registration process is stored in the application database until it is encrypted, serialized and submitted to the identity management platform. As it is an early analysis, we did not specify the specific data flows between processes, HAL and hardware components. In this threat analysis, we also did not investigate the possible threats in the ID Management Server and behave it as a black box working system with three simple components: A web server that accepts data, a management platform that communicates with the government officials and a central DB to store information.

Based on this simplified flow, we employed the STRIDE-per-element approach, which offers an organized method for threat analysis using the STRIDE framework. In this approach, we have assessed threats and their corresponding mitigations for each individual system component (entities, data flow, storage and processes). This approach also presents some limitations [38]. For instance, when it comes to external entities, we have only considered the spoof and repudiate threats. This limitation arises because we lack prior knowledge of the design of external entities. Moreover, in the case of data flows, we have exclusively addressed the tampering, information disclosure, and denial of service threats. This restriction stems from the fact that the STRIDE analysis of data flows primarily focuses on threats against the data being transmitted, rather than how that data is interpreted. Consequently, an adversary could potentially eavesdrop on the conversation (resulting in information disclosure), tamper with the data in transit (tampering), or disrupt the transmission of the data (denial of service). As for threats such as Escalation of Privilege and Spoofing, they may be categorized in relation to the process that is receiving the data.

Table 2 summarizes all the possible attacks that we determined for the designed application (Figure 2). This table is a good starting point to determine the possible attack mechanisms, independent of their likelihood to occur or attack strategies. In the next step, we extended this analysis to understand possible strategies to materialize these attacks.

2.6. Tactics and Techniques for each Attack Point

Integrating the MITRE ATT&CK Framework into threat modelling involves mapping its tactics and techniques to the system’s assets, identifying weaknesses and possible attack scenarios, and defining mitigations. This structured approach enhances the threat modelling process by aligning it with known adversary tactics and techniques, allowing for a comprehensive analysis of potential attack vectors, and improving the security posture of the system while adapting to evolving threats.

For each attack point (Figure 3), we identified the goal of the attack, possible tactics and techniques using MITRE ATT&CK Enterprise, ATT&CK Mobile or ATLAS frameworks, and defined possible attacks and mitigations by reviewing the related literature and previous example attacks. In the review process, we followed a snowballing approach in which we first identified the recent review

	S	T	R	I	D	E
Data Flow (From ->To)						
Process ->Application DB		x		x		
Process ->HAL		x				
HAL ->Hardware		x				
Process ->Server		x	x	x		
Management SW ->Central DB		x	x	x		
Store						
Application DB		x		x		
Central DB		x		x		
Processes						
Input Box Information Entering	x	x		x	x	
Starting Camera						x
Run ML Service						x
Display ML Service Output	x	x	x		x	x
Store ML Service Output	x		x	x	x	x
Format Data		x				x
Encrypt Data		x				x
Serialize Data		x				x
Submit Data		x	x	x	x	x

TABLE 2. STRIDE TABLE FOR GENERIC ENTITIES, DATA FLOW AND PROCESSES.

and then examined the recent references that link to this review.

In the end, considering possible threat actors, attack objectives, tactics, techniques, mechanisms and mitigations, we created two summary tables that demonstrate a comprehensive view in two tables: (1) Table 3 summarizes the output of this threat model for the production-time biometrics application in a complete table, and (2) Table 4 lists this analysis for the ML module development flow.

2.7. Extending AI Security towards Responsible Design

While MITRE ATLAS effectively addresses the identification and mitigation of numerous potential threats, it primarily focuses on known technical components within the development process. From a broader standpoint, security analysis for an AI-powered application should encompass the technology’s impact on end-users and potential societal attack strategies that may manifest through socio-technical mechanisms. As an initial endeavour, we employed the ‘Decision Tree for the Responsible Application of Artificial Intelligence’ to enhance our comprehensive threat modelling process. This is especially critical during the initial stages of AI solution development, as decisions made at this early juncture can have enduring consequences for future implementations.

The following items include the questions from the decision tree and our brief answers to each question:

- **How would artificial intelligence be superior to another approach?** In our scenario, the solution is only achievable with ML algorithms. Extracting information from documents and extracting facial features using rule-based systems is infeasible. While we do employ rule-based algorithms in part for fingerprint collection, deep learning models significantly enhance the model’s accuracy in the matching process.
- **Does this tool already exist?** The AI modules of the application exist as separate components, but there is no integrated application that utilizes these modules on-device. Hence, its development re-

ID	Attack Point	STRIDE	Goal of the Attack	Tactics	Techniques	Possible Attacks	Mitigations
P001	Attack through soft input layer	S	Mimicking user interaction	TA0030 - Defense Evasion, TA0034 - Impact	T1516 - Input Injection	Mimicking key and touch inputs via accessibility services	M1012 - Enterprise Policy, M1011 - User Guidance
P002	Attack through biometric input device	S	Accessing input mechanism via physical or digital methods	TA0009 - Collection	T1056 - Input Capture	Spoofing attacks, altered fingerprint submission, fake physical biometric presentation, latent print reactivation, and a wolf attack using MasterPrints etc.	Liveness detection, anti-spoofing techniques, challenge/response, separation of privileges
P003	Attacks on smartphone sensors	D	Corrupting the integrity of the sensor	TA0027 - Initial Access	T1474 - Supply Chain Compromise	Denial-of-service attack (sensor can either deny the service or add filters so that the biometrics can be altered.)	OS and I/O checks before starting the service. M1001 - Security Updates, M1013 - Application Developer Guidance
P004	Attacks through communication channel connecting input device	T, I	Capturing the raw sensor output.	TA0035 - Collection	T1533 - Data from Local System, T1417 - Input Capture, T1513 - Screen Capture, T1409 - Stored Application Data	Hill-climbing attack, brute-force attack, dictionary attack, replay attack	Time-out-lock-out policy, timestamp, one-time password, digital signature, liveness detection, encryption mechanisms
P005	Attacks on on-device temporary database	T, I	Capturing the any kind of user input.	TA0035 - Collection	T1533 - Data from Local System, T1417 - Input Capture, T1513 - Screen Capture, T1409 - Stored Application Data	Hill-climbing attack, brute-force attack, dictionary attack, replay attack	M1006 - Use Recent OS Version
P006	Attacks on communication channel between mobile and DB	T, I, D	Capturing the encrypted data or denial of service.	TA0037 - Command and Control	T1521 - Encrypted Channel	Employ a known symmetric or asymmetric encryption algorithm	This type of attack technique cannot be easily mitigated with preventive controls since it is based on the abuse of system features.
				TA0009 - Collection	T1557 - Adversary-in-the-Middle	Network Sniffing or Transmitted Data Manipulation	M1041 - Encrypt Sensitive Information, M1037 - Filter Network Traffic, M1035 - Limit Access to Resource Over Network, M1031 - Network Intrusion Prevention, M1030 - Network Segmentation, M1017 - User Training
P007	Attacks on the feature extraction module	T, R	Overriding the feature set to alter the outcome	TA0041 - Execution	T1603Scheduled - Task/Job	Trojan horse attack, Override feature extraction module	Code signing, a Trusted Biometric System, specialized tamper-resistant hardware
				AML.TA0004 - Initial Access, AML.TA0007 - Defense Evasion AML.TA0011 - Impact	AML.T0010 - ML Supply Chain Compromise, AML.T0015 - Evade ML Model, AML.T0031 - Erode ML Model Integrity	Crafting adversarial data	AML.M0003 - Model Hardening, AML.M0006 - Use Ensemble Methods, AML.M0010 - Input Restoration, AML.M0015 - Adversarial Input Detection
P008	Attacks through outgoing communication channels connecting the feature extraction module	T	Injecting false data into channel or trying for reuse-of-residual attempt	AML.TA0006 - Persistence	AML.T0020 - Poison Training Data	False data inject, reuse-of-residuals	Challenge-response based system, disposable Feature Extractors (FE)
P009	Attack on template protection techniques module	D	Extracting information related to the key used in the encryption algorithm	TA0001 - Initial Access	T1195.003 - Supply Chain Compromise: Compromise Hardware Supply Chain	Side-channel attacks	M1046 - Boot Integrity, Signal Masking
P011	Attacks on template database	T,I,D,E	Unauthorized access through external compromised system. Possibly, stealing, deleting, modifying, substituting, and reconstituting the stored templates	TA0042 - Resource Development	T1650 - Acquire Access, T1583 - Acquire Infrastructure	Unauthorized access through external compromised system, steal, delete, modify, substitute template	Server hardening, database access controls, digitally signing templates, template encryption, storing template on card
P015	Attack on decision module	R, D	Overriding the decision module to attempt a denial-of-service by rejecting all submitted biometrics, or allow the system to accept the biometrics of a non-enrolled individual	TA0104 - Execution	T0821 - Modify Controller Tasking	Override decision	M0945 - Code Signing
				TA0103 - Evasion	T0849 - Masquerading	Disguise a malicious application or executable as another file	M0945 - Code Signing, M0938 - Execution Prevention, M0922 - Restrict File and Directory Permissions

TABLE 3. THREAT MODEL FOR THE PRODUCTION-TIME BIOMETRICS APPLICATION. GREEN-COLOURED ROWS INDICATE TTMS FROM MITRE MOBILE, ORANGE-COLOURED ROWS - MITRE ENTERPRISE, AND GREY-COLOURED ROW - MITRE ATLAS. THE ATTACK POINTS AND POSSIBLE ATTACKS ARE DETERMINED BASED ON [16]'S BIOMETRICS SECURITY REVIEW.

ID	Name	Goal of the Attack	Tactics	Techniques	Possible Attacks	Mitigations
D001	Attack in data collection	Resulting in some bias or altering the output.	AML_TA0003 - Resource Development AML_TA0004 - Initial Access AML_TA0006 - Persistence	AML_T0019 - Publish Poisoned Datasets, AML_T0020 - Poison Training Data AML_T0010.002 - ML Supply Chain Compromise: Data AML_T0020 - Poison Training Data	Adversarial Example in the Physical domain	AML.M0001- Limit Model Artifact Release, AML.M0005 - Control Access to ML Models and Data at Rest, AML.M0007 - Sanitize Training Data
D002	Attack to data storage	The attacker can aim to obtain some data or alter the data to change the output	TA0040 - Impact	T1485 - Data Destruction, T1486 - Data Encrypted for Impact, T1565 - Data Manipulation,	Perturbation attacks, Poisoning attacks, Data Leak,	M1041 - Encrypt Sensitive Information, M1041 - Encrypt Sensitive Information, M1029 - Remote Data Storage, M1022 - Restrict File and Directory Permissions
D003	Attack through training	The attacker aims gaining access to model architecture to perturbate model outputs or gain access to filesystem.	AML_TA0002 - Reconnaissance AML_TA0004 - Initial Access AML_TA0001 - ML Attack Staging	AML_T0000 - Search for Victim's Publicly Available Research Materials AML_T0010.003 - ML Supply Chain Compromise: Model	The adversary can use this information to identify targets for attack, or to tailor an existing attack to make it more effective Model poisoning, input manipulation, availability attacks (Gradient and GAN-based)	AML.M0000 - Limit Release of Public Information AML.M0007 - Sanitize Training Data, AML.M0005 - Control Access to ML Models and Data at Rest AML.M0007 - Sanitize Training Data, AML.M0005 - Control Access to ML Models and Data at Rest, AML.M0008 - Validate ML Model AML.M0017 - Model Distribution Methods
D004	Attack through testing	Testing is a part of training process, so all the tactics and techniques are valid for this AP. But, we included this attack point for additional attacks.	AML_TA0000 - ML Model Access AML_TA0000 - ML Model Access	AML_T0044 - Full ML Model Access AML_T0044 - Full ML Model Access	Gaining full white-box access to Incomplete Testing in Realistic conditions	Bias and fairness checks, Benefiting AI Governance methods
D005	Attack on trained model storage	Degrading the performance or reverse engineering.	TA0040 - Impact AML_TA0011 - Impact	T1485 - Data Destruction, T1486 - Data Encrypted for Impact, T1565 - Data Manipulation, AML_T0031 - Erode ML Model Integrity	Perturbation attacks, Poisoning attacks, Data Leak, Model stealing, Reprogramming deep neural nets, ML Supply Chain Attack, Model inversion, Membership Inference attack, Distributional shifts	M1041 - Encrypt Sensitive Information, M1041 - Encrypt Sensitive Information, M1029 - Remote Data Storage, M1022 - Restrict File and Directory Permissions AML.M0003 - Model Hardening, AML.M0006 - Use Ensemble Methods, AML.M0010 - Input Restoration, AML.M0015 - Adversarial Input Detection
D006	Attack through inference	They misuse the system, run expensive queries, or exfiltrate private information via ML Model Inference API Access.	AML_TA0010 - Exfiltration AML_TA0011 - Impact	AML_T0024 - Exfiltration via ML Inference API AML_T0034 - Cost Harvesting, AML_T0045 - ML Intellectual Property Theft, AML_T0048 - System Misuse for External Effect	Inferring Training Data Membership, Inverting ML Model Prompt crafting	AML.M0002 - Passive ML Output Obfuscation, AML.M0004 - Restrict Number of ML Model Queries, AML.M0004 - Restrict Number of ML Model Queries, AML.M0005 - Control Access to ML Models and Data at Rest

TABLE 4. THREAT MODEL FOR THE ML MODULE DEVELOPMENT. ORANGE-COLOURED ROWS INDICATE TTMs FROM MITRE ENTERPRISE, AND GREY-COLOURED ROW - MITRE ATLAS.

quires dedicated efforts for quantization and model shrinking.

- **What kind of training data were used to train the algorithm?** The selected open-source models use public open-source datasets. However, we acknowledge that we need more diverse data to align with industry standards and make our application more robust.
- **Can the training data be gathered in a way that respects ethics and human rights?** We have two possible approaches: (1) Synthesizing a new, balanced, and diverse dataset following a privacy-preserving approach, or (2) collecting data from the real world. However, the real-life data involves highly sensitive PII, such as fingerprints and facial biometrics, necessitating a carefully crafted data collection process if pursued.
- **Are the training data verifiable? Based on the answer, how confident can one be of their accuracy?** We also need to design a diverse set of test cases that demonstrate various inclusivity challenges and different environmental conditions to rigorously verify the accuracy of the model.
- **Will the applicability of the training data to the problem change over time or according to other variables like geography? Can these changes be addressed?** We cannot actively collect new training data, but we can continuously improve the model based on collected features without personal identifiers. In this case, it is essential to verify the system's performance every time it undergoes updates.
- **What are the possible disparate impacts of your tool's application?** Without testing in real-life applications, it's challenging to develop context-specific safeguards to address stakeholder concerns. Special attention must be paid to vulnerable populations. Despite developing the application with industry experts and conducting interviews with various NGOs and SMEs, there is a possibility of encountering disparate cases.
- **Could the application involve emergency limitations on fundamental rights?** The application is designed to address challenges related to accessing fundamental rights. However, as a precautionary measure, we should subject the model to evaluation by an independent third-party assessor to ensure that it doesn't inadvertently infringe on fundamental rights.

Answering these questions supports the development of technology in alignment with responsible innovation principles and the consideration of alternative security mitigations. For example, the response to the first question can provide the most effective approach to mitigation and eliminate all the risks. Following these diverse interaction guidelines and adhering to responsible innovation can foster alternative discussions within an interdisciplinary approach, as further detailed in Section 3.1 and 3.3.

2.8. Integrating this Solution into a Real-life ID Management System: MOSIP

This extended threat model provides a comprehensive analysis of security considerations for the development of a remote national ID registration system. However, it is a hypothetical scenario aimed at enhancing the affordability and accessibility of the registration process. In practice, designing government services in the digital realm is a complex and challenging task that also necessitates careful consideration of other factors, such as server-side interactions and field implementation. Integrating a solution into a trusted, open-source, and standard-compliant platform can preemptively address most security concerns. To demonstrate the potential real-life application of our solution, in this section, we also explain the requirements for integrating our solution into MOSIP (Modular Open Source Identity Platform) [27], an open-source platform designed to facilitate the development and deployment of scalable and interoperable identification systems. To address government-level security concerns, MOSIP outlines strict security requirements for both the enrollment and authentication processes.

In our scenario, the mobile device becomes a registration and authentication tool, replacing the entire system that some readers may be familiar with from their country's passport centres. A MOSIP-compliant biometric collection device should provide a trusted environment, and there are different levels of trust in enrollment and registration processes [26]. L0-trust is a software-level trust with no hardware-related mechanism. Since we cannot sign the data with hardware-level keys, the scenario with L0-trust should be conducted in controlled environments with trusted government officials. L1-trust is provided by a secure chip with a secure execution environment, allowing us to use these devices for both enrollment and authentication.

Mobile device manufacturers and chip providers have been integrating independent security chips into mobile devices to store sensitive data encrypted with hardware-level security for some time. Companies like Samsung with KNOX [31] and Google with Titan [10] provide these security mechanisms, enabling us to use mobile devices at the L1-trust level. However, in disadvantaged areas, we cannot guarantee the accessibility of these devices with security chips or ensure regular security updates from manufacturers that help maintain the L1 status. Therefore, for real-life deployment, the next steps involve exploring verifiable credentials and encryption mechanisms to achieve the L1-trust level at the software layer.

3. Towards a Threat Model for Mobile IUIs

Throughout the threat modelling process, we focused on conducting a high-level analysis of threats to produce a tech-stack-agnostic model. This approach led us to create a flow that can be used and applied for most of the mobile intelligent user interfaces. Our threat modelling process consists of three main stages: (1) Case analysis, (2) Threat assessment, and (3) Extended assessment. The first two stages demonstrate similar steps to traditional threat modelling approaches (e.g. TARA). We started

Figure 4. The taxonomy of attacks on mobile intelligent mobile user interfaces.

the *case analysis* by decomposing the user journey and defining the interactions through the mobile application use. Then, through the *threat assessment*, we identified attack points and assessed threats using STRIDE and MITRE ATT&CK frameworks. Finally, in our *extended assessment*, we focused on the AI development process, and human-system and human-surrounding interaction to present an extended analysis of the possible threats.

This approach presents a practical path for fundamental security analysis in mobile IUI development. In this section, upon the presented threat modelling approach, we discussed three main elements to present a unified approach towards developing a holistic threat model for mobile IUIs: (1) An attack taxonomy, (2) Security principles for mobile applications, and (3) Responsible innovation considerations.

3.1. Attack taxonomy

An attack taxonomy is a systematic classification or categorization of different types of cyberattacks. It is a way to organize and describe various methods and techniques that malicious actors use to compromise the availability, integrity and privacy (confidentiality) of computer systems, networks, and data. Considering the possible attacks in our use case, we extended the NIST’s Adversarial ML taxonomy [39] with [11], [13], [43], [45] to cover the main components (hardware, software, AI model and data [20]) of a mobile IUI. Figure 4 illustrates this taxonomy. In this taxonomy, an attacker has three objectives: Availability breakdown, integrity violations, and privacy compromise. For each objective, an attack might occur on the model, data, device and software. For each attack, an adversary must leverage some capabilities.

This part of the attack taxonomy represents a unified understanding in order to enhance the technical comprehension of security considerations within the mobile IUI domain. It encompasses the key components of an intelligent application from a capabilities perspective. However,

as elaborated in the previous sections, an IUI interacts with humans and its environment. In this context, an IUI can be regarded as a sociotechnical system, necessitating the integration of a sociotechnical approach for a comprehensive security analysis. To facilitate this comprehensive evaluation, we have employed Weidinger et al.’s [41] ”Sociotechnical Safety Evaluation.”

Although the taxonomy presented in [41] primarily focuses on AI safety, we can interpret their three-layer approach within a security context. This approach is broken down as follows:

- 1) *Capabilities* encompass the core technical components, including the AI model, data, hardware, and devices. The number of capabilities is directly proportional to the total time and effort required for threat analysis.
- 2) *Human/environment interaction* addresses context-specific risks wherein individuals may be misled due to the evolving outputs produced by AI algorithms. These environmental and context-specific factors can vary based on the particular AI system in use, the end-users, and the interaction-level characteristics of an application.
- 3) *Systemic impact* focuses on the broad, far-reaching effects of potential threats. This could include impacts on public knowledge ecosystems, trust in the technology, or innovation as a whole. For example, a public-level security concern for a popular intelligent interface can result in a negative image of AI innovation overall.

This three-layer approach, with its detailed breakdown at the capabilities level, represents our initial effort to construct a comprehensive taxonomy for mobile IUIs.

3.2. Security Principles for Mobile Applications

Explicit security considerations for mobile devices are necessary due to the widespread use of these devices, which store sensitive personal data, have diverse attack surfaces, are constantly connected to the internet, and can often be lost or stolen. The diversity in mobile operating systems and apps, coupled with user behaviour, introduces security vulnerabilities, making it crucial to address issues like malware, app security, and data protection. To safeguard against possible threats, both users and developers have the responsibility. To promote security in mobile devices, both iOS and Android publish security principles and communicate them with their developers regularly. Mayrhofer et al. lists five main principles that guide the Android platform security model [21]:

- 1) **(Multi party consent)** The execution of an action should only be possible when all stakeholders—the user, platform, and developer—reach an agreement. Consequently, data stored in shared locations are controlled by users, data within private app directories are managed by apps, and data in system locations fall under the control of the platform.
- 2) **(Open ecosystem access)** Generic app-to-app interaction is supported and app developers can create their own APIs as the Android project is an open ecosystem.
- 3) **(Security is a compatibility requirement)** The Compatibility Definition Document (CDD) outlines all the systems, starting processes, sandboxing, and isolation procedures. Any modification that alters these procedures renders the Android OS invalid.
- 4) **(Factory reset restores the device to a safe state)** Without system software reinstallation, Android returns to the original secure state by wiping the data partitions.
- 5) **(Applications are security principals.)** Apps are not fully authorized agents for user actions. It is the main difference between a mobile and desktop/server OS.

These principles prevent attackers from tricking users into giving access to data controlled by other apps. All these principles should also be an integral part of the security plan in mobile UI development.

3.3. Responsible Innovation

Responsible innovation is an approach that emphasizes ethical, social, and environmental considerations throughout the development and deployment of new technologies. Key principles include anticipation of potential impacts, reflexivity in self-assessment, inclusivity of diverse stakeholders, responsiveness to feedback, transparency in information sharing, accountability for ethical and legal standards, sustainability, and a focus on the common good [35]. In our use case, we employed the AAAS decision tree as an initial step towards considering these aspects of responsibility. However, responsible innovation requires an interdisciplinary approach that involves working all the development teams together, continuously. It requires

careful consideration of the consequences of innovation and aims to balance the promotion of technological advancement with the protection of societal well-being.

Combining knowledge from human-computer interaction (HCI), responsible AI, and responsible innovation, we summarized a brief set of considerations for developing more secure and responsible software systems as follows [2], [5], [8], [18], [22], [23], [28], [30], [35], [37], [42]:

- **Ethical Considerations:** Prioritizing ethical design and avoiding harm can naturally promote fairness, transparency, accountability, and privacy.
- **User-Centered Design:** Ensuring the design of an accessible, learnable and usable system can help users see possible security concerns and understand potential issues beforehand.
- **Transparency and Explainability:** Providing clear explanations can help users intuitively grasp the internal working mechanism of software and data, which might foresee some possible issues beforehand.
- **Fairness and Bias Mitigation:** Regularly auditing and mitigating biases in AI algorithms to ensure fair treatment of all user groups and continuously monitoring algorithms to rectify emerging bias issues can help ML developers identify attacks in their data collection and storage phases.
- **Inclusivity and Diversity:** Ensuring software is accessible to users from diverse backgrounds and cultures and promoting diversity within the development team to enhance inclusivity can accelerate a more robust development process for secure software systems.

These three main discussion points, the presented attack taxonomy (Section 3.1), Mayrhofer et al.'s mobile security principles (Section 3.2) and our curated responsible innovation concerns (Section 3.3), represent a holistic approach by bringing knowledge from different domains such as responsible software development, integrating principles from HCI, responsible AI, and responsible innovation. In our use case, bringing this academic and commercial knowledge into the threat model process led to considering a more informed perspective in producing mitigations. We hope our use case and discussion on this extended security analysis can help practitioners bridge the knowledge gaps between diverse teams in their businesses to achieve complete and effective threat models.

4. Conclusion

This paper describes our approach to threat modelling for a representative mobile intelligent user interface, presenting a more generalized perspective that can be applied by practitioners in various fields. We followed a narrative that developers with limited security analysis experience can also apply the steps. Building upon existing methodologies, our approach extends beyond mere technical considerations. We underscore the fact that the ultimate frontier in threat modelling for Intelligent User Interfaces (UIs) necessitates interdisciplinary discussions to better incorporate security by design into our development process. A comprehensive understanding of how

users, potential attackers, and other stakeholders may interact with these interfaces in diverse contexts is crucial for enhancing security measures.

Our threat modelling process encompasses three principal stages: (1) Case analysis, (2) Threat assessment, and (3) Extended assessment. The initial two stages share similarities with traditional threat modelling approaches, such as TARA. We initiated the "case analysis" by dissecting the user journey and defining interactions within the mobile application. Subsequently, in the "threat assessment" phase, we pinpointed potential attack vectors and evaluated threats using the STRIDE and MITRE ATT&CK frameworks. Lastly, in our "extended assessment," we delved into the AI development process, as well as the interactions between humans, systems, and their surroundings, providing an extended analysis of potential threats.

In conclusion, the threat modelling process expounded in this paper furnishes a solid foundation for securing mobile IUIs. By holistically addressing the technical, contextual, and human aspects of threat analysis, we can develop more robust and secure IUIs in an age marked by ubiquity and complexity.

Data Availability

This paper contains all the essential knowledge and data needed to replicate our research. We relied on publicly available documents and scholarly works to shape our threat modelling approach. Deliberately, we condensed all the content to fit within the conference page limit, forgoing the use of an appendix in order to maintain a seamless flow.

Acknowledgements

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